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Data Review

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Abstract

The Life in Kyrgyzstan Study (LiK) provides a rich longitudinal dataset tracking households and individuals in Kyrgyzstan from 2010 to 2019. LiK's longitudinal structure follows the same households across waves, enabling dynamic analyses of employment, migration, well-being, exposure to shocks, social networks, and political preferences.

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Review of the Life in Kyrgyzstan Study

by Stas Gorelik

The Life in Kyrgyzstan Study (LiK) provides a rich longitudinal dataset tracking households and individuals in Kyrgyzstan from 2010 to 2019. The baseline sample includes approximately 3,000 households selected through stratified two-stage random sampling across all seven oblasts and the two major cities, Bishkek and Osh, using the 2009 census as the sampling frame. This design ensures national representativeness and coverage of both urban and rural areas. The study comprises seven waves: the first collected in late 2010, followed by waves in 2011, 2012, 2013, 2016, and 2019.

LiK's longitudinal structure follows the same households across waves, enabling dynamic analyses of employment, migration, well-being, exposure to shocks, social networks, and political preferences. (For details on specific modules, see the questionnaires for each wave.)

As in most panel studies, attrition poses important challenges, resulting in about 77% of the original households remaining by the sixth wave. Researchers, therefore, should carefully consider how attrition may bias longitudinal analyses, particularly for respondents who move, drop out, or otherwise change status. Moreover, differential attrition, common in low- and middle-income contexts, may disproportionately affect higher-mobility or more vulnerable households, potentially undermining representativeness over time. Analysts should test for such patterns.

Data access: The dataset can be downloaded only after filling out a data request form. Link to the dataset: <https://dataverse.iza.org/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.15185/izadp.7055.1>.

Related publications (selected):

- Brück, T., D. Esenaliev, A. Kroeger, A. Kudebayeva, B. Mirkasimov and S. Steiner (2014): "Household Survey Data for Research on Well-Being and Behavior in Central Asia". *Journal of Comparative Economics*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 819-35.
- Egamberdiev, B., Bobojonov, I., Kuhn, L. & Glauben, T. (2023). "Household resilience capacity and food security: evidence from Kyrgyzstan." *Food Security*, 15(4), 967-988.
- Freudenreich, H., Aladysheva, A. & Brück, T. (2022). "Weather shocks across seasons and child health: Evidence from a panel study in the Kyrgyz Republic." *World Development*, 155. DOI: 10.1016/j.worlddev.2021.105801.
- Tertytchnaya, K., De Vries, C. E., Solaz, H. & Doyle, D. (2018). "When the money stops: fluctuations in financial remittances and incumbent approval in Central Eastern Europe, the Caucasus and Central Asia." *American Political Science Review*, 112(4), 758-774.